

DEVELOPMENT OF LOW COST “*IN-SITU*” Ti/TiB AND Ti-6Al-4V/TiB COMPOSITES

M. Garcia de Cortazar¹, J. Coletto¹, J. Goni¹, M. Bausa¹, F. Dartigues² and Y. Le Petitcorps²

¹ *Non ferrous Metals & Metal Matrix composites, INASMET FOUNDATION
Mikeletegi Pasealekua, 2, E-20009 Donostia –San Sebastian, Spain*

² *ICMCB/ENSCP-B-UPR 9048-Université Bordeaux1, Avenue du docteur A. Schweitzer, 33608 Pessac cédex,
France*

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INTRODUCTION

High technology transport sectors are looking for higher performance materials, competitive in terms of cost, lighter than conventional titanium alloys and recyclable, which could improve efficiency of several components and reduce fuel consumption through weight reduction. Although novel anisotropic Titanium Reinforced Composites (TMCs) reinforced with continuous SiC CVD filaments were developed some years ago, and are commercially available, they are still very expensive in comparison with other MMCs or with conventional titanium alloys. During the fabrication of these SiC_{CVD}/Ti composites, there is a chemical reaction at the filament/matrix interface which influences badly the mechanical properties of the composite. In order to decrease the cost of the composite material and to improve its chemical stability, it has been proposed to obtain the reinforcement during the preparation of the composite itself using a similar procedure that the preparation of alloys reinforced with a second phase. These composites materials can be called “*in-situ*” composites. The advantage is the chemical stability between the reinforcing phase and the matrix, the draw back is the difficulty to find the adequate reinforcing phase. More over, in order to have a composite effect, the second phase has to be stiff enough, the volume fraction has to be adjusted at minimum to the critical volume fraction of reinforcement and lastly the second phase must have a fibre shape in order to present a sufficient aspect ratio (Length/diameter) L/d higher than the critical value of 10 in order to permit a load transfer between the 2 constituents. Previous researches have proved that the titanium monoboride (TiB) full-fill these requirements [1]. The TiB has an orthorhombic crystal structure, an acicular shape, its stiffness is in the range of 450-550GPa, the analysis of the binary phase Ti-B phase diagram shows that the volume fraction can be adjusted as required and the TiB has a thermodynamic equilibrium with the titanium. The “*in-situ*” precipitation can be done in the solid or the liquid state of the matrix. A lot of papers have been published during the last decade on the fabrication of these composites through the powder metallurgy (PM) technique and some composites or even components are today commercially available [2]. The PM composites have to be forged and/or machined in order to achieve the right shape of the component. Few attempts were done with the casting routes where as the casting process can be an alternative way to reduce even more the cost and also to prepare more complicated shapes for example by using the investment casting process technology.

Therefore the main aim of this investigation is twofold: (1) preparation of “*in-situ*” Ti/TiB composites via a newly developed cost effective process called Self propagating High

temperature Synthesis (SHS), (2) melt these composites with a titanium alloy (Ti-6Al-4V or Ti-64) using a conventional investment casting route.

In the present paper, the microstructure and mechanical properties of the composites produced in an investment casting industrial foundry will be analysed. Although different casting alloys have been investigated to be used as matrix in the final composites, the main efforts have been done with the Ti-6Al-4V (Ti-64) matrix, which is the most widely use titanium alloy for cast components in aeronautics or other fields.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The process developed at INASMET (N° PCT/ES03/00596) to produce “*in-situ*” composites consists on the production of billets of Ti/TiB master compound with a very high volume fraction of TiB that is further melt together with titanium ingots using a common Vacuum Arc Remelting (VAR) process. The volume fraction of TiB in the final product is controlled by the proportion between the Ti/TiB master compound and the titanium alloy.

Preparation of the master compound (1st Step)

The master alloy is prepared by the newly called SHS process, in which a blend of reagents (Ti-sponge and amorphous boron powders) when ignited, spontaneously transforms into a product (Ti/TiB) composite due to the exothermic heat of the reaction (Figure 1).

Fig. 1: Principles of the SHS process (a) ignition, (b) and (c) propagation and melting, (d) end of the reaction.

The potential advantages of this process in terms of processing and cost are:

1. The simplicity of the process: it can be done in air even with titanium and boron powders; the simplicity of the equipment,
2. The low energy requirement: only a local heating is necessary in order to ignite the reaction and the process itself needs no more additional external energy,
3. The high purity of the products: impurities are evaporated during the process due to the high temperature of the combustion wave.

This process presents however few drawbacks:

- The high volume fraction of boron which is necessary to propagate the reaction makes the Ti/TiB composite very difficult to machine or to cut,
- The presence of included gas which makes a porous material. The porosities can be closed by the application of a pressure during the propagation; this is quite easy as the titanium is liquid during the propagation of the wave.

In the SHS process, the theoretical maximum temperature can be calculated from the heat capacities and enthalpies of formation and transformation. This temperature is called the adiabatic temperature (T_{ad}).

Fig. 1: Theoretical adiabatic temperature (T_{ad}) and % of titanium liquid phase versus of the TiB content.

In the SHS reaction investigations, T_{ad} is an indication whether the reaction will become self-sustaining or not. In fact, based on an empirical criterion suggested by Munir et al, the adiabatic temperature must be equal or higher that 1800K, [3]

The raw materials used are reported in Table1.

Products	Morphology and structure	Average particle size (μm)	Chemical of composition of the impurities	
			O (Wtppm)	C
CP Ti Grade 3	Angular and crystallised	130	3300	1200
Ti sponge	Porous and crystallised	<150	1200	130
Boron powders	Granular and amorphous	2-3	80	-

Table 1: Powders characteristics

Reactants of titanium and amorphous boron are first blended in a Tubular mixer with alumina balls for around 24 hours, cold compacted into cylindrical pellets using an uniaxial press up to 60% of apparent density of the theoretical value. Once the compact pellet is prepared it is put inside a mould. The base of the mould is filled with fine sand which is covered with a thin layer of diatomite to act as a thermal insulator. At the top, a tungsten wire is placed for the ignition of the reaction. The heated tungsten filament at the top end ignites the pellet at 700°C and the self sustained combustion wave propagates through the all pellet (see Figure 1). The compact is pressed few seconds after the ignition while the product is still in the hot and plastic conditions. Once the synthesis reaction is completed and the master composite samples produced, the materials need to be machined and cleaned in order to eliminate the sand and impurities onto the surface. The main steps of the cleaning method consisted in: (1) Water-jet cutting to eliminate the rough surface, (2) Wire cutting to machine the upper and lower surface of the sample, (3) Final polishing of the sample.

Preparation of the Ti-64/TiB“in-situ” composite (2nd Step)

Afterwards, the TiB is introduced inside the melt by welding the master compound of Ti/60%TiB on a consumable titanium alloy (Ti-64) electrode. The process to melt the mixture is a common Vacuum Arc Remelting (VAR) process. When the electrode is melted, the Ti/TiB is also melted in contact with the electrode, the TiB is then dissolved inside the titanium alloy like the temperature is above the liquidus temperature of the Ti-B mixture. The molten composite is then poured into a mould by centrifugal casting. The TiB crystals precipitate within the matrix during the solidification of the mixture. The sample moulding is produced via the lost wax investment moulding technique. The ceramic shell may have an influence on the solidification rate and as a consequence on the grain size of the matrix.

RESULTS

Microstructure of the master compound (1st Step)

Figure 3 illustrates the microstructure of the as-reacted master material after the SHS step under pressure. The material is fully dense and the acicular crystals which are observed have been identified by XRD as TiB compounds. The composition of this material is 60% of TiB (Wt%).

Fig. 3 : SEM microstructure of a master compound prepared by SHS (Ti with 60%Wt of TiB)

The morphology of TiB is a rod like morphology, with diameters around 2-5 μm and lengths around 5-20 μm . Some clusters of TiB are also present due to the high volume fraction of TiB inside this material. The acicular form of the TiB whiskers has been explained by Zhang et al. The crystal structure of TiB is a B27 class orthorhombic structure and the boron atoms are zig-zagging along the [010] direction which is the growth direction of the crystal.

Microstructure of the in-situ composite after remelting (2nd Step)

The Ti-64 unreinforced alloy results in a very characteristic microstructure such as individual alpha lamellar packets having a common orientation with them within the prior beta grains (figure 4a). The TiB needles have a strong influence in the microstructure, because they significantly refine the microstructure. The composites produced by this process present a very fine microstructure due to the presence of the TiB at the prior β grain boundaries (Figures 4b and c, Figure 5).

Fig. 4: Microstructure of as-cast samples (a) Ti-64 alloy, (b) Ti-64/TiB hypoeutectic composition, (c) detail the microstructure (from (b)).

Fig. 5: Grain size measurements under ASTM E-112 standard.

The tensile tests were carried out following the standard EN 10002-1/2001, at 2mm/min and a different temperature conditions (room, 300°C, 400°C) in air. The tensile tests specimen were flat specimen, the geometry of the specimen was given by the EN 10002-1/2001 standard.

Table 2 summarized one set of the tensile test data of an hypoeutectic composition (0.5 TiB/Ti-6Al-4V) and compared it to the cast Ti-64 alloy.

	Yield Strength 0.2% (MPa)			UTS (MPa)			Strain at max. Load(%)		
	25°C	300°C	400°C	25°C	300°C	400°C	25°C	300°C	400°C
Ti-64/ 0.5TiB	890	570	500	1000	730	670	18	18	19
Ti-64	840	525	460	930	660	600	15	23	20

Table 2 : Average values of the most important tensile parameters of the cast composite (0.5% TiB/Ti-64) and the cast matrix (Ti-64)

The improvement in tensile properties is explained by the grain refinement effect of the TiB. The amount of TiB in this composite is not sufficient to promote a composite effect (load transfer) as expected in common composite materials. For the same reason, with this amount of TiB the stiffness cannot be increased. This low amount of TiB was chosen in order to give a sufficient ductility to the component. On the one hand the TiB has an influence on the

ultimate and yield strength of the composite, on the other hand if too much TiB is added, the ductility is drastically decreased. The reason of this is explained by the fracture behaviour (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Fracture surface of the composite tested in tension

Due to the presence of the stacking faults inside the TiB crystal, when the composite is tested, the TiB cleaves according to specific crystallographic planes and the prior crack can propagate within the slip planes of the titanium matrix whereas the fracture surface of the titanium alloy is always ductile. When the volume fraction of TiB is increased, the distance between two TiB crystals is decreased and the cracks can easily propagate from one TiB crystal to the other as a consequence, the ductility of the composite is rapidly decreased. The poor bonding between the atoms in the TiB crystal is probably the main drawback.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The composites produced by this process present a very fine microstructure which provides a very attractive combination of mechanical properties. Besides the mechanical properties of Ti-64/TiB composites, the simplicity of the manufacturing procedure developed constitutes a realistic alternative in a medium short term to replace at a reasonable cost conventional cast parts for aeronautical, automotive and other advanced components.

The process has been validated in an industrial investment casting facility. Some general conclusions obtained from the characterisations of cast parts are:

(1) Increasing the volume fraction of the reinforcement improves both the strength to failure and the Young's modulus. By contrast, the higher the TiB content, the lower the ductility. A compromise has to be determined with the volume fraction in order to get strength and ductility at room temperature. (2) At higher temperatures (300-400°C), the improvements in strength is even better in comparison with the unreinforced matrix and the ductility is still present.

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